

TREMLES AND NOISE IN PRODUCTION, THEY HAVE A REASON TO COME AND SOURCES AND PROTECTION MEASURES MEASURES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11353563>

Abstract: noise and vibration factors harmful to human health in the field of labor protection and life safety are considered. Noise and vibration negatively affect human health and performance. This article outlines noise and vibration criteria and measures against it.

Key words: noise, vibration, vibration noise, compressors, pumps, machine.

It came out of the car and the engine shook and attempts to reduce the sound that has been going on for, and currently improve the quality of preparation of these details, the use of materials which generate less noise, to the right choice of gear, and the timely replacement of the details like I am eating is carried out by way of.

As it is known, as a result of gas and liquid in the tube would yield aerohydrodynamic noise is to be tried. In addition, such sounds, fans, compressors, pumps and youuv the performance of the engine at the time of the occurrence of internal comes. As a result of the movement of the liquid and the gas, the noise aerohydrodynamic circular had happened, for the reason that it does not give them the same in small to reduce the source of the noise. Therefore, the level of such noise noise noise to the way of attenuators is reduced through the installation of.

The noise in electrical machines and electromagnetic devices that character appears. Such noise main cause variable magnetic field influence ferromagnit of mass shaken it is. In transformers such noise packs dense nesting and dempfer (shaken to decrease commercial, absorbent) material use through reduced.

Shtrembled to food and classification, the set of protection measures: the fight against noise and tremors machines, equipment and technological processes in the initial stages of designing of the purpose of the beginning is in accordance with [2].

In the process of drafting the general plans of the enterprise, of course, the necessity to be put fighting measures against noise.

Thus, basically, to a place of noise high workshop, there are as far as possible, placing them to the side the production of the edge of the territory, from the other sound insulation barrier blocking with noise high workshop to special sound insulation of doors and windows of the building It's noisy should be made of special materials.

Measures to reduce noise at the source which produces to fight against it, starting from the first move should be. Machines, equipment and quality of the equipment installation, repair and timely coordination of its power dynamic, will give good results.

Some devices have the power of dissolving properties of sound waves. Noise noise waves porous absorber falls to the surface of the material when trying to bring spending most of the power in the narrow part tebranma noise is porous to air. The heat capacity of the power noise air heater shrunk porous and as a result the cycle to the external environment as

a result of the spread and the noise will disappear.

The fight against noise to another method of proper selection of technological processes, machines, equipment, technological processes and equipment that would work at lower voltages them to ensure quality and timely collection of the performance of repair work is also of great importance. Shaken to the fight against consists of the following events:

Work areas, equipment and construction equipment from the effects of the vibration machine generated constructions saved is a method of blocking one of the methods to be shaken to perfect.

In this method its basis rope between oscillating mechanism with elastic fabric, cloth a part of the vibration is reduced somewhat due to be pass on to win in the case that the vibration amount is significantly reduced. Set or trembling amortizatorlar spring steel, rubber and other elastic material is prepared from. Machines, equipment, the equipment use of order-do not follow the rules, a rough violation of the instructions as a result of work of the equipment leads to tramp works so silently.

The development of the project is done when the noise of the struggle against the production, the production process begins from the period of in the selection and enforcement. To this event, enter the following: at the source of the noise reduction using noise barriers in the way of lowering. The process of improvement of work procedures and equipment, enterprises acoustic architectural planning of buildings and equipment.

As a result of any warehouse or rotary movement in the longitudinal aerodynamic, mechanical and electromagnetic noise. This is different to a decrease in interactions we have to gear conductor 5-10 db in the space, find the end of slits, has the details of a pet, especially, on their own time and in action is enough to anoint quality repair parts. Aerodynamic and electromagnetic interactions and the screen blocking and feature a special coating used to having to win. The particular design of buildings and buildings, and inserted them without damaging a lot of noise region near to the distance in accordance with the requirements of standards or sanitary enterprises are placed.

Production buildings and auxiliary buildings and projects made them when away from the room less noisy equipment is installed in a room as possible tramp are placed. a lot of noise acoustic screens to protect from the noise of the workers who work in the building or sound yutgich lids, stand at a distance management, building finishing materials for walls and ceilings sucker sound, with the sound of the room to get protected from the rest of the arrangement, the rotary movement of the machine or the parts available vibration damper device - from the foundation to establishing the necessary event and others.

2.1.-the picture. Against headphones noise:

1-plastic shell; 2-glass fabric; 3- whisperer diaphragms; 4-removable

Personal protection tools must have the following characteristics:

-noise level should be reduced to the amount of sanitary norms;

-talk do not lower the essence of the word when necessary;

-ear pain is to strong pressure should be giving out above;
-risk-free stimulant and aesthetic strangled must meet the requirements should not a sound from me.

performance noise. The main part of the noise spread through the air, taking any obstacles put in his way if the pressure is reduced by a certain amount.

Tremors and noise effects arising from the occupation of diseases

The ministry of health 06.06.2000 y. The number 300 [order](#) 8-quotes in the app list of professional diseases, [5].

Professional diseases list

2-table

N	the name of the disease	that earned the emergence of diseases is likely to lead to dangerous, harmful substances and the factors of production	Directory done , which is the approximate list
1	2	3	4
	Vibration disease.	Local production, which passed into the hands of workers in the work place for a long time and a regular vibration the vibration of the impact.	To sway , causing out and the hands with the working of the machine to vibrate causes which work place.

Vibration (tremors) disease (WK)- professional patient one; of vibration (rather shocked) to the people for a long time the effects of whatever come out. Tremors (lot. Vibratio "kolebanie, baking powder") — mechanical vibration, and trembling, the meaning refers to, [6].

The disease will be the night and the character trembling of the power and tattoo related; such tremors gavin's known part (e.g., capture), partial vibratsiya] and whole body (general vibratsiya) impact will be. Some in the profession, those using hand instruments tattoo or them properly use cannot, gavin wrong to keep, cold, noise and other(s) vibratsiya his patient the cause of be can.

In times of crisis, diseases, hands, paws zirqirab og`browsing and be toliqib, frost irritability, head pain, rapid fatigue, irritability, heart-vascular activity in serious changes and others is observed.

Treatment of the disease is the cause of the toe`present factor possible as early more eliminated from being is. Various drugs, physiotherapy treatments, the appropriate resort toe`lish complex treatment outlined into the structure of enters.

Initial appearance.

Peripheral angiodistonik syndrome in the hand, fingers, sometimes angiospazma Hand sensor polinevropatiya vegetative syndrome WK II-stage. Average expressed the view Peripheral angiodistonik syndrome in the hand, fingers and frequent angiospazm Vegetative vegetative disorders steady polinevropatiya syndrome with sensor:

- Hand fingers angiospazmalar
- Hand in miofibroz and bone - changes distrofik
- Neck - shoulder plexopathy
- Tcerebral syndrome angiodistonik

WK III –stage. Expressed a clear view:

Sensor-motor syndrome polinevropatiya

Entsefalopolinevropatiyalar

General Polinevropatiyalar with akroangiospazmalar.

Preventive treatment measures in the event of the iri

1. The preventive primary functions:

a) technical b) san gigienik v) to choose professional

2. Secondary preventive task settings:

- Five wk in advance , identify signssh.
- WK check out patients clinic.
- the identification of occupational diseases.
- medical-boilogik factor (factor risk) determine (osteoxondrozi the spine, the disease xafaqon, yu an, chronic neuroinfections, neuropathy, long-term professional work experience (10 y.>)

Periodic medical examination times per year vibration effects in healthy working working I pass. Multivitamins health conditions in the spring time points (undevit, aevit v. b.) a preventive course is recommended.

Dangerous group (risk grupp) - a medical examination, periodic times per year. The course of preventive treatment 2 times per year – spring and fall (in the context of zdravpunkt). In addition to venoruton vitaminli plaques from therapy, or with a solkoseril geparin maz massage (self-massage), gymnastics and gidroprotseduralar of treatment is recommended.

Unsuitable,. Dynamic track. 2-to the moon. MKV Outpatient, treatment and stationary profilaktoriy (year of iga 1.)

Methods and tools of protection from shook

Protection from the effects of tremors, design stages start and all the equipment in the passport of the noise and the trembling figure, depending on the most convenient is selected. Thus, there are tebranuvchi and noisy warehouse buildings, and a separate, placing the edge of the wind direction across the territory will be worthwhile.

Methods of reducing the harmful effects to the rise trembled in the source can be divided into two groups. When lowering the power in the first source causative trembled, trembled with the latter bound with their foundation building constructions and other equipment in place and led to decrease.

Reducing the source trembled to the rise in machine, equipment, arsenal on the set of quality repair them in their own time, anointed to stand on the work order them in moderation without straining the organization and work to ensure that the proper use of weapons and clothing and personal protection equipment remote control creates the possibility to achieve the expected results.

Lowering the vibration at the source if possible to you, then it trembled to its foundation with the basis of rubber or spring or between the source suppressor putting amartizatorlar will be reduced. The most effective method of reducing shaken, oscillator

equipment vibration or less replaced with equipment that unwavering the most improvement. For example, iron in a workshop by way of improved equipment vibration compacting concrete concrete production, that is, a group of independent oscillating dampers dwarf in the bottom of his craft, set in the threshold of the building to reduce the noise level and overall vibration also dramatically out of it is born.

Spreading often experience tremors decrease the effects of commercial activities in engineering from the warehouse directly to the development and implementation of will come. For lowering the fluctuations in this regard, vibration barrier, vibration damper, vibration reverser and effective use of tools:

- a) vibration barrier two types of passive and active form;
- b) vibration damper vibration through the floor of the building from the source and the other is set to the device to avoid the effects of the foundation;
- v) vibration reverser it demfirlash method is called and the rubber over the barrier, or mastika is plasticity in surroundings.

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